

Eric Marantz

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Eric Marantz's speculative theory of a possible fourth spatial dimension:

I have believed for many years that the fourth dimension of space could be called the zoom or scalar (scale) dimension. Synonymously it could also be called the size dimension... most importantly, it seems to possibly carry significant implications in the philosophical metaphysical sense because it appears to display an uncanny symmetry, not only in the equal distance of the smallest orders of magnitude currently known such as the plank length and the observable universe from our human size scale on the surface of the Earth, or in other words, it seems significant that we appear to reside in approximately the middle of the scale or spectrum extending from the extremes of the microcosm to the macrocosm (which could be explained by the limits of human perception, meaning we can only see so far in either direction, even if the spectrum continues further or infinitely) but more strikingly, the fact that the patterns of matter being generally orbitals and spirals seem to fractally, exponentially, or perhaps logarithmically decrease in density in other words the distance of orbiting particle patterns seems to increase at the same exponential rate in both directions of the anthropocentric symmetry meaning whether you zoom in or out from the human size scale the distance between orbital patterns seems to increase exponentially as in less particles of matter and more empty space dissolving into total emptiness at both poles... i.e. the background radiation of the observable universe macrocosm or the quantum foam at the plank length microcosm